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Bhutan-IRRI Project: Local tradition meets modern know-how

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The small landlocked kingdom of Bhutan has a stunningly beautiful terrain of mountains and trees, and a colorful Buddhist culture. It also faces a challenge that is even larger than the nearby Himalayas: it must feed a population that is growing at about 3% y^{-1} . Food security is a key element in the Bhutan-IRRI Project, a successful collaboration among Bhutan's national agricultural research and extension system (NARES), Canadian donor International Development Research Centre (IDRC), donor Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC), and the IRRI.

Achievements of the Bhutan-IRRI Project

1. Founded a national agricultural research system
2. Created a growing base of trained Bhutanese researchers and extensionists
3. Increased the access of Bhutanese farmers to new technology
4. Began screening rice varieties for blast resistance
5. Diversified the Bhutanese diet
6. Intensified cropping to produce higher yields of food items
7. Established links to governments and organizations around the world
8. Generated a growing body of research literature on agriculture in Bhutan

The challenge

Population growth and food security in Bhutan

Bhutan's king, His Majesty King Jigme Singye Wangchuck, has always had a strong personal interest in problems that affect his country. He is interested in agriculture, which has a tremendous impact: it provides a livelihood for about 79% of the population and contributes about 37% of the gross domestic product or GDP. Bhutan's high rate of population growth (about 3% y^{-1}) is of further interest; it increases the demand for food.

In 1983, the Royal Government of Bhutan requested a project proposal from international organizations. In response, IDRC and IRRI submitted a project proposal titled "Rice Farming Systems Research" that aimed to build the capacity of Bhutan for rice research. Acceptance of this proposal set in motion a remarkable process.

Given the kingdom's high rate of population growth, Bhutan must continue to increase food production. The limited availability of cultivable land is a significant challenge to this goal. Also, migration of Bhutanese from the farm to the city creates a labor shortage on the farm and a need for more human resource development to keep up with the changing job market. Bhutan plans to meet these challenges by continuing its research on water use, agricultural productivity, soil fertility, and forest management within the context of the country's integrated farming systems.

Training

Building upon Bhutan's knowledge base

Many generations of Bhutanese have studied abroad. Bhutan has lacked in-country facilities to train agricultural scientists, but, in recent years, it has overcome numerous obstacles to human resource development. Since the project's inception in 1984, the project has trained 40 Bhutanese research and extension staff in short-term nondegree courses at IRRI. Another 200 Bhutanese agriculturists have participated in short-term nondegree IRRI courses in Bhutan. These activities have greatly assisted Bhutan in building a knowledge base to conduct its own agricultural research and development.

Until the early 1990s, a shortage of university-trained personnel within the kingdom to teach at the tertiary level meant the absence of a Bhutanese national university or other centralized training facility. "A lot has changed since the mid-90s when we sent large batches of people out for diploma and certificate courses," noted Sangay Duba, program

director of the Renewable Natural Resources Research Center (RNRRC)-Bajo.

By 1999, an important change in trend was taking place: increased self-reliance for education and training in Bhutan. The kingdom had begun to offer in-country training with Bhutanese instructors. In addition to the nondegree IRRI courses, one-time in-country training courses have taught extension staff to carry out germplasm collection and preservation. At agricultural conferences and workshops outside Bhutan, Bhutanese agriculturists have enhanced their skills and developed international collaboration in agricultural research. Participants in these courses, conferences, and workshops have brought the latest technical knowledge directly to Bhutanese farmers.

Farmer involvement

Learning from farmers' expertise

Since 1984, the Bhutan-IRRI Project has created a closer partnership among farmers, extension staff, and agricultural researchers in Bhutan. Farmer input has been invaluable to extensionists and researchers. The first Bhutanese researchers were pioneers, says Sangay Duba. No one in the world at that time had experience doing exactly what the Bhutanese were setting out to do: establish a research system within Bhutan's unique local conditions.

Pirithiman Pradhan and Ganesh Chettri began their agricultural research careers in Bhutan, right out of college. Right away, they encountered difficulty when they designed experiments in the field. "[Both of them (Pirithiman and Ganesh)] had theory but no experience," says Sangay Duba. "[They] had studied experimental designs for flat areas. Here [in Bhutan] we have small terraces. How to base a trial on such topography is a problem." Eventually, the researchers learned to tailor their research trials to the local conditions.

Few people knew as much as local farmers did about local conditions. Direct contact between farmers and trained agricultural specialists forged a particularly important information link. Most of the country's farmers lacked reading and writing skills, knowledge of the English language, telephones, electricity, and access to literature that could help them produce more food.

Farmers provide information that helps the agricultural ministry to understand and document local farming practices and preferences, and to allow for a better fit among farmer needs, extensionist

expertise, and researcher goals. The Bhutanese government also serves as a resource in screening new technologies, thus helping farmers to adopt practices and inputs that are best suited to their priorities.

Local committees provide the main medium through which farmers give their input. By encouraging the use of a village's social infrastructure to communicate and solve problems, the renewable natural resource (RNR) sector of Bhutan is setting in place activist farmers. Active community involvement and the necessary resources can only improve the ability of a local group to realize its vision for the future.

The teamwork of farmers, extensionists, and researchers during the blast epidemic in 1995 shows the cooperation and communication that the three groups have built over the years. Today, farmers provide vital information to researchers through their involvement in Gaynekha Field Days and other efforts to study the blast pathogen.

A specific problem

The 1995 blast epidemic in Bhutan

Rice blast disease is the most destructive disease of rice and exists in virtually all rice-growing countries. "Blast" describes affected fields, which appear to have been "blasted" by a flamethrower. The disease is caused by the fungus *Pyricularia grisea* and can affect all aboveground parts of the rice plant.

Bhutan's first recorded outbreak of rice blast swept through the higher elevations (1,800–2,700 m) in 1995. The epidemic affected just under 730 ha of rice and resulted in the loss of nearly 1,100 metric t of rice. Hundreds of farmers lost their entire rice crop that year and risked having no seeds to plant in 1996 because of having no harvest in 1995.

Scientists from IRRI went to Bhutan to identify the cause of the epidemic and find ways to prevent future outbreaks. Bhutan had already begun to assess the damage as well as options for alleviating the losses of farmers. Visiting scientists helped to develop strategies that would prevent such outbreaks in the future.

One positive outcome of the crisis was that the Ministry of Agriculture (MoA) and the RNR sector in Bhutan proved capable of responding effectively. In addition to damage assessment, the MoA formulated a long-term strategy to contain any future epidemics of rice blast. The shuttle breeding program, begun in 1987 in collaboration with IRRI, had

identified promising lines for medium- and high-altitude rice environments in Paro.

Planning and implementation of this strategy, along with the introduction of new vegetable crops, have helped Bhutan to improve the kingdom's food security. Not only have farmers increased domestic yields of rice, they have also diversified their diet.

Improved varieties

More food, less poverty

Initially, the Bhutan-IRRI Project looked at Bhutan's agricultural research development from a rice-as-commodity perspective. As the project progressed, in addition to working on varietal improvement of rice, it looked at cropping patterns—what farmers grew, how they grew it, and when.

Not long ago, daily Bhutanese meals consisted almost exclusively of chilies, soft cheeses, and maize. A family also would eat the local short-grain red rice if it had grown enough. Occasionally, an egg and some chicken, pork, beef, or yak meat also spiced up the meal. Today, there are many additional options, thanks to changes in cropping patterns and new varieties of staple plants.

How did this cropping revolution begin? Researchers and extensionists encouraged crop diversification to improve soil health and increase food production. The diversification of crops brought about improved types of food—radishes, bulb onions, aubergines, potatoes, tomatoes, beans, and many other foods—that farmers could sell locally or in Thimphu, the capital city. Market forces, associated with the buying and selling of this food, began the transformation of Bhutan from a bartering system into a cash-based economy.

Perhaps Mr. Dorji, a local farmer, best sums up the recent changes in Bhutan's cropping patterns: "The total yield from the farm and total income for the farmer have increased." With such tangible benefits for the farmer, it seems likely that more farmers will diversify the types of food they grow and eat, and build a stronger market economy and a brighter future for their children.

Home-grown improved varieties

Increasing rice yield in Bhutan

The RNRRCs have been working toward the goal of increasing Bhutan's self-sufficiency in rice production. Because of the country's steep terrain and other factors, it is not possible to increase the area of rice. However, it is possible to increase yield by

growing rice more intensively on existing area by using improved high-yielding varieties.

In 1984, researchers began to introduce and test improved high-yielding varieties from other countries such as Nepal and the Republic of Korea, which had similar climates. They also collected, evaluated, and preserved several local varieties of rice. Farmers liked the option of trying out new varieties in their fields because it was relatively nondisruptive to their longstanding practices.

In 1985, Bhutan and IRRI began the shuttle breeding program. Bhutan sent germplasm (seeds/plant material) of its local varieties to the Philippines, where IRRI plant breeders crossbred them with improved varieties and sent back F₂ seeds for field evaluation and selection in Bhutan.

After using more than 40 traditional Bhutanese varieties as parents, the shuttle breeding program produced a lot of materials. By 1992, researchers introduced and evaluated 5,440 varieties at various research stations in Bhutan. Less than one-third of the materials were found to contain the sought-after traits, but Bhutan now had a germplasm resource base upon which to build.

The year 1999 marked a milestone in Bhutan's rice improvement efforts. Through the rice varietal improvement breeding program at the RNRRCs, Bhutan formally released four promising lines for cultivation in mid-elevation (700–1,500 m) valleys. These are the first-ever high-yielding varieties that were developed entirely within Bhutan. Some lines are the result of crosses between IR64—the most widely grown rice variety in the world—and local red and white rice varieties.

The table compares yield performance in on-farm trials of the new lines with a control group of farmers' local varieties. On average, improved lines yielded 23% higher than the local checks, and helped the Bhutanese to combine new research with local preference.

Linkage

Bhutan shares tools and ideas with international organizations

For decades, agricultural scientists have based their research efforts on their best estimate of the needs of farmers. A one-way flow of information from researcher to farmer produces technology that is not always useful to farmers. Today, more two-way dialogues are happening at the individual and organizational levels. The Bhutan-IRRI Project helps the Royal Government of Bhutan (RGoB) to understand and articulate the needs of farmers, extensionists, and researchers. The kingdom now has valuable connections with donor agencies and governments that are interested in basing agricultural research on a better understanding of the needs of farmers.

Externally funded development efforts support the ability of Bhutan's research team to reach farmers by funding a particular research center in the kingdom. RNRRC-Khangma receives support from the International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD). RNRRC-Jakar receives backing from a project for livestock research in central Bhutan, funded by the SDC, a major donor to the Bhutan-IRRI Project. RNRRC-Yusipang receives support from an SDC endeavor for forestry research.

Additional resources come from externally funded projects that round out the resource base for RNRRC-Bajo's research in Lingmuteychu watershed. The Water Management Research Programme (WMRP) has been funded by the Netherlands Development Organization (SNV) and has built a foundation for water management upon which the Bhutan-IRRI Project has been able to build. The nationwide Horticultural Development Project, assisted by the United Nations Development Programme, links with RNRRC-Bajo to support its research on fruits such as citrus, stone fruit, and others. This research promises to help local families manage their land more sustainably.

Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) of released varieties in farmers' field trials, 1995-98.

Breeding line/variety	1995	1996	1997	1998	Mean	% yield increase over local check
Bajo Maap-1	6.0	5.6	7.1	7.0	6.4	19.6
Bajo Maap-2	6.8	6.6	4.9	6.3	6.1	14.2
Bajo Kaap-1	7.2	5.8	6.8	7.1	6.7	25.6
Bajo Kaap-2	6.8	6.8	7.8	7.2	7.2	33.4
Local check varieties ^a	5.8	5.3	5.0	5.3	5.4	—

^aVariety names: Zakha, Tan Tshering, local Maap, local Kaap. Source: Improved Rice Varieties Released for the Medium-Altitude Valleys of Bhutan.

Community-based natural resource management *Environmental protection through teamwork*

Now that Bhutan has resources in place to sustain its own RNR research system, decisionmakers can foster a localized, grassroots approach to solve the country's natural resource problems. The kingdom continues its quest for long-term sources of funding, but the RNRRC network is a powerful testament that the leadership of Bhutan now has a foundation upon which it can build and bring more knowledge and resources into local communities.

Community-based natural resource management (CBNRM) centers scientific investigations on a well-defined local area, which minimizes logistical problems during research. Localized studies strengthen farmer participation, support a more interdisciplinary approach to research, and reinforce linkages among farmers, extensionists, and researchers. The goal of this approach is to understand better the interaction between resources and users on the scale of a watershed, as well as the interaction between and use of off-farm and on-farm resources.

In 2000, a community forestry planting was part of the Bhutan-IRRI Project's effort to protect the nation's natural resources and to understand better the role they play in the integrated farming systems. At the Lingmuteychu watershed, about 55 local villagers and researchers planted seedlings of several varieties of native trees: poplar, oak, *Leucaena*, and pine. These seedlings offer hope for restoration of this badly degraded area and promise to rehabilitate the land over the long term so that it can provide a livelihood for future generations.

Conclusions

The kingdom of Bhutan has priceless assets: the uniqueness of its culture and the beauty of its natural resources. At the same time, it faces an urgent challenge: provide enough food to keep pace with a population growth rate of about 3% y^{-1} .

To help Bhutan meet this challenge, the IDRC- and SDC-funded Bhutan-IRRI Project has worked to build the capacity of the NARES by promoting the following practices: training, farmer involvement, improved varieties, new cropping practices, linkages with international organizations, and CBNRM. Since 1984, Bhutan has increased its rice yield, developed its in-country expertise, diversified its daily diet, and begun its shift from a bartering system to a more market-based economy.

Bhutan's continuing transformation demonstrates how much change the country has undergone in a fairly short time. In just 18 years, Bhutan has learned to combine landmark scientific breakthroughs, such as improved rice varieties, with its own century-old practices for sustainable resource management. The country has also successfully built up its capacity for the creation and dissemination of rice research. Bhutan's progress is certain to inspire developing countries and donors to use both local tradition and modern know-how to meet the day-to-day needs of our world's people.

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The Fertilizer Advisory, Development and Information Network for Asia and the Pacific

<http://www.fadinap.org>

The Fertilizer Advisory, Development and Information Network for Asia and the Pacific (FADINAP) web site was launched in 1997 to provide information in the Asia and the Pacific region on a wide range of fertilizer-related topics. It features several databases and directories: the Agrochemicals Bibliographic Database, a directory of Sources of Fertilizer-related Information, Database on Pesticides and the Environment, and Fertilizer Statistics. FADINAP's bibliographic database is probably the first and only online database with special emphasis on fertilizer. It contains more than 8,000 citations and abstracts of publications related to fertilizer and crop protection in Asia and the Pacific. The online fertilizer directory contains more than 2,000 addresses of organizations involved

in the fertilizer industry. The database on Pesticides and the Environment is comprehensive on aspects of pesticides used and their effects on the environment and human and animal health in selected countries in Asia. Fertilizer Statistics is a ready statistical reference on fertilizer indicators such as consumption, production, imports, and exports. This statistical database is also linked to the statistical databases of the Food and Agriculture Organization (UN FAO), Asian Development Bank (ADB), International Fertilizer Industry Association (IFIA), World Bank (WB), Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific (ESCAP, Thailand), International Monetary Fund (IMF), and United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO, Austria). Time-series data on monthly retail prices in selected Asian countries and current trends of f.o.b. prices of fertilizer are also available for free.

The site also offers information exchange and communication tools for agriculture professionals and other stakeholders in the fertilizer sector in the region such as a virtual library of electronic documents with search and document submission facilities. It allows users to post electronic documents to the Web site for immediate sharing with other users. News concerning the fertilizer and agrochemicals sector in Asia and the Pacific can also be found. The site also contains a buy-and-sell bulletin board that creates a virtual fertilizer market allowing users to post advertisements to purchase or sell fertilizer products/services free of charge. It also contains links to Web sites of academic, research, and government institutions and international and regional organizations and centers related to the fertilizer sector.